

Determinants of Consumer Behavioral Intension towards Clothing Brand in Pakistan: The Role of Brand Personality Appeal

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Abstract

This study is regarding to Brand Personality Appeal (BPA) and what is the impact of simplicity, emotionality, aggressiveness, activity and responsibility on consumer's attitude and intention. The main determination is to find out the impact of these variables on brand personality appeal. The data was collected with the sample size of 361 which includes 153 male respondents and 208 female respondents. The tests utilized to interpret the data are Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Analysis of a Moment Structures (AMOS). In addition, the research is conduct on the basis of brand personality appeal (BPA) because brand personality plays a significant role for customer loyalty and also impact the consumer's attitude towards the brand because the brand image is like a human personality and both are built over the period of time. Our main variable of the study is activity, responsibility, aggressiveness, emotionality and simplicity.

Keywords: Brand personality, brand personality appeal, consumer attitude, and behavioral intension

1. Introduction

This study is centered on the branding theory of social marketing service; this theory is focused upon how the perception of the company's product is created in the mind of its consumers. The consumer develops the perceptions about the product or service offered by the company on the basis of the communication being received from various sources and the experience they obtain by the offer given by the company. In this study a model shows a dependent and independent relation between different variables and the brand personality, simplicity and emotionality has a direct and negative relation with the brand personality and compared to it aggressiveness, responsibility, and activity has a direct and positive relation with brand personality showing that the all five variables are independent and brand personality is dependent on each of them, on the other side where brand personality is independent with attitude behavioral intension, showing the indirect relationship of activity, responsibility, aggressiveness, simplicity, and emotionality with the attitude and behavioral intension.

Moreover, brand personality plays major role for the customer's loyalty and it effects the overall consumer's attitude and their behavioral intentions toward brands. Giving a brief summary of the related topic brand personality is a set of human appearances that officially reflect to a brand name, because of brand personality and brand equity increasing in an effective manner (Aaker, 1997). In other words, brand personality relies on previous impressions and it also like a human personality because both are unique and both are built over a period. Brand personality also establishing the significant role in maintaining and influence consumer's attitude and behaviors (Sirgy, 1982). There is a five factors model of brand personality that reflect the consumers toward brands and these are responsibility, activity, aggression, simplicity and emotionality (Aaker, 1997). This model of brand personality depends on the big five personality qualities bases on neuroticism, openness, agreeableness, extraversion, and conscientiousness that came from emotional discipline (Tupes and Christal, 1961). In this study brand personality appeal BPA also highlighting under the backgrounds of brand personality that is also important for the study. Defining the key term, brand personality appeal BPA is an ability of brand that attract consumer through its personalities traits. Brand personality appeal is something that how to attract customers and maintain their loyalty through communications that what the brand deliver to their customers. There is a three factors model of brand personality appeal that reflect the consumer positivity toward the brand and these are favorability, originality and clarity (Freling, Crosno, and Henard, 2011). In the literature, the relationships in this study can easily be defined as, the five factors model of brand personality namely; responsibility, activity, aggression, simplicity and emotionality have significant and insignificant direct relation with brand personality appeal (BPA), which has a direct relationship with consumer's attitude and behavioral intention. That means the five-factor model has indirect relationship with consumer's attitude and behavioral intention. The study shows that the brand personality appeal has a positive influence on consumer purchase intention under the background of model of brand personality appeal (Freling et al, 2011). The research also demonstrates the impression of brand personality and brand personality appeal on attitudes of consumer and intentions in social and commercial marketing domains. Establish the importance of the topic study also indicate the relationship between brand and consumer in different dimensions and how does it effects the minds of the consumer based on commercial and social marketing. Social marketing takes progressive results through marketing strategies that influence individual and societies (French and Gordon, 2015). Social marketers also enhance the

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services to increase and build the interest of costumers on social marketing (Zainuddin, Russell-Bennett, and Previte, 2013). The commercial marketing idea directly reflect on social marketing without adjusting (Peattie and Peattie, 2003). In testing the relationship, this research reacts to Peattie and Peattie (2003) who condemned that there is an influence of the commercial marketing concepts on the social marketing and are transferred in to it without any changes or adoption. There is some main point like, developing brand trust loyalty, built positive brand image and influencing consumer behavior are the significant concern in commercial marketing (Farris, Bindle, Pfeifer, and Reibstein, 2010).

In preceding years, studies have been conducted to discover the impact of brand personality and brand personality appeal on consumer attitude and behavioral intentions towards social and commercial marketing. In addition to it, these researches conducted globally. In Pakistan there is least researches conducted on the perspective of brand personality and brand personality appeal so most of the customers are not fully conscious about the role of brand personality in their attitude or behavioral intentions. Brand personality BP plays a significant role in making customers loyal to the certain brand and it effect the total customer attitude and behavioral intention toward brands. Brand personality is like a social appearance that reflects to a brand name and because of its brand equity increasing in effective way (Aaker, 1997). In other word brand personality, also play a major role in maintaining and influence consumer's attitude and behavior (Sirgy, 1982). Brand personality having a five factors model that reflects consumer towards brands and these are responsibility, activity, simplicity, aggression, and emotionality (Aaker, 1997). Recent study also indicate that the brand personality also stimulates brand attitude, image, commitment and purchase intention (Eisend and Stokburger-Sauer, 2013). According to Molinillo, Japurta, Nguyen, and Chen, (2017), a responsible brand is a strong analyst of loyalty and trust in the minds of consumer than the active brand and active brand is a strong analyst of awareness in comparative to responsible brand. Brochado and Silva, (2015) specified that top of the mind of consumers brands are market with clearly and unique brand personality but small subgroup of brand personality characteristic assists as a major criterion for brand positioning. Lin, (2010), found that brand personality has a direct and positive relation with agreeable personality trait and extroversion personality trait, sincerity, competence and sophistication brand personality has direct and positive relation with loyalty, and agreeableness and openness has a significant positive relation with loyalty. In this research, brand personality appeal BPA also emphasizing under the contextual of brand personality that is essential for the study. Describing the key term, brand personality appeal is a skill of brand that fascinates customers through its personality's qualities. Brand personality appeal is approximately that how to attract customers and maintain brand trustworthiness through communications. Brand personality appeal having a three factors model that reflects consumers towards brands and these are favorability, originality and clarity (Freling, Crosno, and Henard, 2011). Brand personality appeal gives consumers a motivation to buy one brand over another (Keller, 1993). In the research model, five factors of brand personality have major and minor relation with brand personality appeal (BPA), which has a straight relationship with buyer's attitude and behavioral intention, which shows the five-factor model has indirect relationship with buyer's attitude and behavioral intention. The research demonstrate that the brand personality appeal has a positive effect on consumer buying intention under the contextual model of brand personality appeal (Freling et al, 2011). Consequently, this study tends to find out that what is the relationship between brand personality appeal, and how they influence the behavioral intention and attitude of the customer under the local clothing brands in Pakistan.

2. Literature Reviews

2.1. Theoretical background

2.1.1. Branding theory of social marketing service

This research is based on the branding theory of social marketing service, which elaborates that how a firm desires its goods to be acknowledged in the buyers' thoughts. It is an insight that buyer makes of a firm's goods or services constructed on the message they obtain from diverse sources and the knowledge they obtain from the proposal given by the firm.

2.1.2. Responsibility and Brand personality appeal (BPA):

Responsibility have direct and positive relation with brand personality appeal, the service that is selected for the study is banking sector these services are linked with credence services and require specialized knowledge for greater outcome, furthermore responsibility also require expertise and technical quality Ostrom and Iacobucci (1995).

2.1.3. Activity and Brand personality appeal (BPA):

The relationship of activity with brand personality appeal is direct and positive because it is mainly concerned with managing and maintaining relationship with employees on the other hand, credence service has high involvement and complex as compared to other services McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001).

2.1.4. Aggressiveness and Brand personality appeal (BPA):

Aggressiveness has direct and negative relation with brand personality because it is more associated with negative thoughts and perception. In banking sector aggressiveness is associated with safety and security issues Lancaster (2005).

2.1.5. Simplicity and Brand personality appeal (BPA):

Simplicity also impacts brand personality appeal in negative manner because credence services are more complex and incompatible with the characteristics of simplicity that is why it is lead towards negative attitude McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001).

2.1.6. Emotionality and Brand personality appeal (BPA):

Emotionality have direct and positive relation with brand personality appeal because banking services are considered as high involvement services therefore the risk taking is also high with respect to financial safety and security so they cater their clients through emotional association McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001).

2.2. Empirical studies

Esmailpour (2015), The appeal of efficient and representative brand relationships on brand reliability, investigated with the data collection of 450 persons with birth year in between 1977 to 1994 in the of the study were propose by using the test LISREL concludes that perceived quality of a brand country Iran while taking sunglasses and watches as their two luxuries brands in this study. The findings is better to indicate the brand loyalty and brand attitude, with brand personality, brand prestige, brand tribalism have indirect positive affect on brand loyalty.

Anselmsson et al. (2014), Brand appearance and purchaser's enthusiasm to pay superior amount for food brands. Demonstrate in the study that respondents were choose randomly by sending mail of the questionnaire to 850 people who were fully in charge of the household purchasing of groceries between the ages of 24 to 74 years old. Explorative factor analysis with single and multiple regression analysis shows the conclusion that quality is one of the most important factor of determinant about price premium while adding other variables doubles the expectedness and accepting of the price premium. Social image, uniqueness and home country origin were most important direct determinants while CSR customer service responsibility and awareness were the indirect factors.

Balmer and Greyser (2006), examine the corporate marketing tactics, which they apply in a corporation to successfully run a venture that includes, corporate branding, corporate communications, integrating corporate identity, corporate reputation and corporate image respectively all together they make an organization marketing strategy strong to satisfy their customers. They have collected a sample data by rigorously analyzing the literatures that was related to the history of marketing thoughts. The study focused on the following variables namely marketing strategy, corporate identity, corporate communication, and image and branding. Moreover, to check the sample data originality they have integrated British and US perspectives on this particular study to comprehend the facts that was related to the corporate marketing. Additionally, the findings of the study suggest that all six tools of marketing strategy including corporate image, reputation, branding must be focused under one platform of corporate marketing and they are linked with one another therefore equally importance must be given to each element.

Wang and Yang (2008), find out that whether country origin impacts the relationship between brand personality and purchase intention in emerging economies. For this reason they have collected a sample data by doing cross city survey of China auto industry to basically check the hypothesis that was actually predicted on a sample of 1200 respondents of Sino-German joint venture's auto brand of Bora. In order to further validate they collected another sample of Japanese venture Honda auto brand. The variable considered for the study was Brand identity, consumer behavior, brand identity and the country origin that was China. Additionally, the sample date was tested by using a moderator that provides theoretical insights about the factors that was influencing consumer purchase decision making and gave a knowledge on whether to emphasize brand origin or not. Moreover, the findings to the study were brand personality and COO both creates a significant impact on the purchase intention of a consumer. Furthermore, COO image results in creating a positive impact in the relationship between purchase intention and brand personality where as a negative COO image will drop down the positive brand personality which ultimately affects the purchase intention. Therefore, companies that have a high COO image and a high brand personality will result in the consumer having a greater purchase intention than those with weak brand personality and having a negative COO image.

Louis and Lombart (2010), examines the effect of trust, attachment and commitment towards the brand. They have collected a sample data from 348 young French consumers the age of those consumers are from 19-23. The variables they have considered are brand personality trust in the brand, and attachment to the brand and commitment to the brand. Additionally, the sample data was tested by applying structural equations modeling, Cronbach's alpha and Jo`reskog's rho coefficients, and exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses. The findings of the study suggested that all the personality traits of Coca Cola brand had a directly impact on any one of the three social outcomes under review: trust, attachment, and commitment to the brand. Furthermore, they have an indirect impact as well on the personality traits on commitment by means of trust and attachment to the brand.

Belaid and Behi (2011), find out an empirical examination in the useful consumption framework in which they discuss the role of attachments in building the consumer brand relationships. They have collected a sample data from the two sources in order to define the relationships between the development of brand attachment and the experiences and significances of brand attachments. The initial study focuses on the scales and the test of psychometrics properties of it and the second study is focused on relationship between the variables which is hypothetical in the model. They have used the variables in their study are brand attachment, brand satisfaction, brand trust, loyalty, and brand commitment. Additionally, sample data was tested by applying scales structure and reliability, and the model fit. The finding of the study concludes that the brand attachment is considered as a

vital contribution to brand commitment for useful items. The structural model confirms most of the theorized connections.

Rindell and Strandvik (2010), analyzed the corporate brand images which is advancing in buyers' regular daily existence they have discussed corporate brand development in their study. They have collected the sample data from receiving the company's branding strategies by utilizing the pre-determined dimensions. They have used the variables in their research are revolves around brand renovation, brand evaluation, brand building and brand emerging. Furthermore, sample data was tested by applying a conceptual discussion and a framework which represents the map of the four alternatives of brand image. The findings of the study suggested that the corporate brand development is recommended as a method for including consumers' everyday brand image developments and re-developments in an organization's marking procedures. They further discussed that the corporate brand development depends on two new ideas: picture legacy and picture being used. They proposed a model in their research for understanding developing a dynamic corporate marking

Kim (2000) studied Analysis of brand identity and brand assertiveness inside the clothing product classification in United States of America. The sample size of this study was over 500 women of age 18 or over. The researcher mailed a questionnaire to the people and received voluntary replies and concluded that irrelevant of the exceptionality of the personality of every brand, the ones with favorable attitude of brand have a favorable 'competent' trait ratings. The trait 'competent' is preferred by the consumers to be present in all of the brands. Quality may be generally indicated through this trait.

Ferguson, Lau and Phau (2016), studied the brand identity as a straight reason of brand addition achievement: Does self-monitoring matter? A sample size of 284 undergraduates was selected of age 18 to 24. The researchers used experimental design and focus group to gather the responses and concluded that brand personality fit between the brand extension and the parent brand, that is, the greater the image of a parent brand in customer's mind they will be attracted towards the brand extension.

Su and Tong (2015), produced the research on brand character and brand equity: suggestion from the casualwear business in the United States of America. A sample size of 420 college students was selected to assist the research. The researchers applied Brand Personality Scale (BPS) and revealed that attractiveness, sincerity, competence, innovation, activity, excitement and ruggedness are the seven dimensions to describe a sportswear brand and among these seven dimensions, attractiveness, competence, sincerity and innovation, are four positive factors to enhance sportswear brand equity.

Gordon, Zainuddin, and Magee (2015), examined that explaining the possible of branding in public marketing facilities: Developing brand identity and brand identity call in Queensland, Australia. A group of 395 women with the age of 50 to 69 was selected as the sample size of the study. The researchers applied multiple mediation models such as bootstrapping approach with Mplus version 6.11 to determine Brand Personality (BP) and Brand Personality Appeal (BPA). The study revealed that both, Brand Personality and Brand Personality Appeal, act similarly in the service types and the customer's behaviour is also affected by it, either directly or indirectly.

3. Methodology

In this study, quantitative approach is used. This study uses correlation research design because correlation design have multiple uses and benefits in quantitative study. The source we used in the collection of data is primary source. This research is conducted in the area of Pakistan geographically the selected target population is taken in the Karachi city (Sindh). The target respondents of the research on which the result will be generalized whom are currently working and studying, and have the knowledge about the brand personality as a marketing perspective. A total of 42.38% are male respondents and 57.61% are female respondents from which the data is collected. The total population of the research will be the target population of the study. The first sample size taken was about 400 respondent data in Karachi Pakistan, after analysis 361 respondent data was left from which the result is made. The remaining 39 responses were outliers in which many missing values occurred and because of that 31 responses data was excluded from the study and the analysis were done on remaining 361 respondent data. This research utilized the quantitative research technique. The instruments used to accumulate the data through questionnaire approach. All variables containing five question each probing question with a total of 40 questions. Questionnaire also contains a demographics factor includes: age, gender, education and income level. To measure the reliability of the data collected, SPSS (statistical package of social science) and AMOS (Analysis of a moment structure) as a statistical technique is applied. On the data KMO and Bartlett's analysis is also applied to enrich the result. In the findings of the study EFA (Exploratory factor analysis), CFA (Confirmatory factor analysis) and Path analysis is applied in order to find out the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

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3.1. Hypothesis

- H1. Responsibility has a significant relationship with brand personality appeal.
- H2. Activity has a significant relationship with brand personality appeal.
- H3. Aggressiveness has an insignificant relationship with brand personality appeal.
- H4. Simplicity has an insignificant relationship with brand personality appeal.

- H5. Emotionality has a significant relationship with brand personality appeal.
 H6. Brand personality appeal has a significant relationship with attitude.
 H7. Brand personality appeal has a significant relationship with behavioral intension.

3.2. Model Hypothesis

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Demographic Analysis

The following demographics are from the collected data for the study of role of brand personality appeal in consumer attitude and behavioral intention from the target population. The data was collected from both genders, male and female. There were 153 male respondents, which concludes up to 42.38% of the total responses, and 208 female respondents are the remaining 57.61% of the total responses. The age criteria were from less than 20, which had 72 respondents and the percentile was 19.94%, age 21 to 25 respondents were 190 and its percentile was 52.63%. age 26 to 30 respondents were 56 and its percentile was 15.51%, age 31 to 35 respondents were 20 and its percentile was 5.54%, and similarly, age 36 and above respondents were 23 and its percentile was 6.37%. In employment factors the public respondents were 24 and its percentile was 6.64%, private respondents were 67 and its percentile was 18.50%, student's respondent were 190 and its percentile was 52.63%, semi private respondent were 15 with the percentile was 4.15%, business respondents were 40 and its percentile was 11.08%, and similarly, others respondents were 25 with the percentile was 6.92%. Eventually, in education sector the undergraduate respondents were 167 with the percentile of 46.26%, the graduate respondents were 122 with the percentile of 33.79%, the master's respondents were 47 and its percentile was 13.01%, the M.Phil. respondents were 12 with the percentile of 3.32%, the PHD respondents were 3 with the percentile of 0.83%, and similarly, the others respondents were 10 with the percentile of 2.77%. however, in the sector of income less than 20000 respondents were 174 with the recorded percentile of 48.19%, the respondents between 20000 to 30000 were 83 with the percentile of 22.99%, the respondents between 30001 to 40000 were 38 and its percentile was 10.52% and similarly, the respondents of 40001 and above were 66 with the recorded percentile was 18.28%.

4.2. Reliability analysis

the value of Cronbach alpha is ranging between 0.632 to 0.864. The minimum criteria of 0.60 is met (Hair et al., 1998; Raza et al., 2016). Thus the reliability test shows the relevance of all the variables and our approximations which can advance for additional analysis. The results are further shown in table 2.

4.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis

A total of 24 items break into 8 areas namely, responsibility, simplicity, emotionality, activity, aggressiveness, brand personality appeal, attitude and behavioral intension. In accumulation, the factor analysis performs on all the items reaching from 0.408 to 0.835 meeting the least requirement of 0.30 for the sample of 350 or above (Hair et al, 1998). Hence the results of factor analysis are shown on table 3.

4.4. Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin and Bartlett's tests of Sphericity for sampling adequacy:

For the study of our sampling acceptability we used KMO and B Bartlett's test of sphericity test values. the Bartlett's test of sphericity value of probability is 0.000 (which is under 0.05). It determines the relationship at 5 percent level of importance is adequate and is suitable for further inspection. Results have been given in table 4.

Table 1: Demographic Analysis

Variable	Frequency	Valid%
GENDER:		
Male	153	42.38%
Female	208	57.61%
AGE:		
less than 20	72	19.94%
21 to 25	190	52.63%
26 to 30	56	15.51%
31 to 35	20	5.54%
36 or above	23	6.37%
EMPLOYMENT:		
Public	24	6.64%
Private	67	18.50%
Student	190	52.63%
semi private	15	4.15%
Business	40	11.08%
Others	25	6.92%
EDUCATION:		
Undergraduate	167	46.26%
Graduate	122	33.79%
Masters	47	13.01%
M.Phil.	12	3.32%
PHD	3	0.83%
Others	10	2.77%
INCOME:		
less than 20000	174	48.19%
20000 to 30000	83	22.99%
30001 to 40000	38	10.52%
40001 and above	66	18.28%

Source: Authors estimation

Table 2: Reliability Analysis:

Variables	Items	Cronbach's alpha
Responsibility	5	0.864
Aggressiveness	5	0.838
Simplicity	2	0.794
Behavior Intension	5	0.823
Attitude	3	0.844
Brand Personality Appeal	2	0.707
Emotionality	2	0.632

Source: Authors estimation

4.5. Confirmatory factor analysis

The structure makes use of eight variables, including activity (Act), aggression (AGG), simplicity, and (SIM). Brand personality appeal (BPA), emotionality (EMO), responsibility (RES), attitude (ATT), and behavioural intent (BI). Based on the study of the research model, Table 4's goodness of fit test indication reveals that the overall model is satisfactory. The CFI is 0.901, TLI is 0, GFI is 0.86, AGFI is 0.871, and RMSEA is 0.073 in this table. This shows that every number is within the acceptable range for the suggested level. For the acceptance of the hypothesis model, Bentler (1990) and Hair et al. (1991) advised that the CFI value should be near to 0.9 and the RMSEA value should be less than 8%. As a result, our model provides sufficient information about its model fitness to the sample data, and it.

4.6. Path Analysis

In this research study the association between the Hypotheses is recommended by using (SRW) Standard regression weight model. In table 6 it shows that activity has a positive and significant relationship with brand personality appeal the p value of H1 is (0.020). As soon as activity increases brand personality appeal increases. In conceptual point of view, it can be explained as when a brand is active and keeps its consumer aware the brand personality appeal increases McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001). The relationship between responsibility and brand personality appeal is positive and significant the p value of H2 is (0.000), when responsibility increases brand personality appeal

increases. In conceptual order it can be stated that the more responsible the brand the more consumer attracts towards the brand Ostrom and Iacobucci (1995). The relationship between aggressiveness and brand personality appeal is negative and insignificant with the p value H3 (0.032). When aggressiveness increases, brand personality appeal decreases. This relationship signifies that if the brand comes on too strong the consumer may lose his/her interest in the brand Lancaster (2005). Emotionality holds a positive and significant relationship with the brand personality appeal, when emotionality increases the brand personality appeal also increases the p value is H4 (0.068). This positive relationship signifies that when the emotional attachment of a consumer with the brand increases it also increases the brand personality appeal McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001). Simplicity has a positive and significant relationship with brand personality appeal and the value of H5 is (0.554), but the result is not supported. If the brand is simple and not innovative enough to bring any new and attractive change it makes a negative impact on the brand personality appeal McColl-Kennedy and Fetter (2001). Brand personality appeal has a positive and insignificant relationship with attitude the value of H6 is (0.000). As the brands enhance itself it increases the brand personality appeal but due to increasing prices the attitude of the consumer's decreases. Brand personality appeal has a positive and significant relationship with behavioral intension value of H7 (0.000), if brand personality appeal increases behavioral intension also increases. This relationship signifies that when the brand personality gets stronger the consumer intends to purchase and utilize more than habitual level.

Table 3: Exploratory Factor Analysis

	Activit y	Responsibilit y	Behavior al Intension	Attitud e	Aggressivene ss	Brand Personalit y Appeal	Emotionalit y	Simplicit y
ACT 1	.745							
ACT 2	.767							
ACT 3	.716							
ACT 4	.741							
ACT 5	.652							
RES1		.678						
RES2		.705						
RES3		.636						
RES4		.785						
RES5		.721						
BI1			.599					
BI2			.559					
BI3			.728					
BI4			.661					
BI5			.639					
ATT1				.835				
ATT3				.781				
ATT4				.825				
AGG 3					.705			
AGG 4					.749			
AGG 5					.783			
BPA1						.814		
BPA4						.787		
EMO 3							.660	
EMO 4							.761	
SIM3								.408
SIM5								.812

Source: Authors estimation

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.905
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity approx. Chi-Square	4542.471
degree of freedom (df)	351
sig.	0

Source: Authors estimation

Table 5: Model Fitness

Model Fitness	CFT	TLI	GFI	AGFI	RMSEA
Threshold values	≥ 0.85	≥ 0.80	Close to 1	Close to 1	≤ 0.05 (> 0.05)
Measurement Model	0.923	0.907	0.88	0.854	0.056
Structural Model	0.901	0.9	0.86	0.871	0.073

Source: Measurement model 27 items, Structural model 27 items. P value < 0.08 or 8%

Table 6: Standardized regression weights for the research model

Hypothesis	variables	regression path	SRW	P value	Remarks
H1	activity	ACT→BPA	0.252	0.020	Supported
H2	responsibility	RES→BPA	0.509	0.000	Supported
H3	aggressiveness	AGG→BPA	-0.11	0.032	Supported
H4	emotionality	EMO→BPA	0.213	0.068	Supported
H5	simplicity	SIM→BPA	0.054	0.554	not-supported
H6	attitude	BPA→ATT	-0.446	0.000	Supported
H7	behavioral intension	BPA→BI	0.94	0.000	Supported

Notes: SRW= standardized regression weights. Dependent variable= brand personality appeal (BPA). P value < 0.10 (10%)

5. Conclusion and Discussion

5.1. Conclusion

The final result shows that all the variable was used are simply meet their benchmark. The variable we use such as, responsibility and activity has a significant and positive relationship with brand personality appeal. Aggressiveness and simplicity has a direct and negative relationship with Brand personality appeal. However, Emotionality has a direct and positive relationship with brand personality appeal.

This study concludes that, the most important variable in this research is "Responsibility" which highly and directly influenced on consumers of local clothing brand in Pakistan, which overcome and increase the attitude and behavior intension of greater buying. Attitude shows the direct and significant relationship with the behavior intention to purchase. Therefore, the person intention is greater to buy local clothing brand in Pakistan.

The second variable which has positivity influenced in this study is "Activity" which shows the positive relationship with behavior intention. According to the findings the results indicates that the more information and knowledge individual have about the local clothing brand greater the intention to buy.

Furthermore, one more variable which has positively influenced in this research is "Emotionality" which indicates the positive relationship with behavior intention. As per investigated result the social norms are playing important role in it such as, if an individual has core knowledge about the local clothing brand than they prefer or recommended to other peoples and society. So it gives positive effect and increase sale of local clothing brand in Pakistan. It simply concludes that emotionality has a positive relationship on behavior intention.

5.2. Recommendation based on findings

the marketers of different firm's organizations who make marketing strategies to capture the market for their product can adopt from the findings of this research to enhance and develop their strategies more to attract the consumer.

Second is the policy makers and from the results of this study they can make better policies considering the latest data and findings.

1. Third is the new entrepreneurs who are willing to start a new business and capture the market, can have the latest information about the market, consumer's behavior intention and attitude towards local clothing brand from the results of this study and adapt the new things in market.
2. Last is the researchers who can in future make this study their base for the research and can adapt from the findings and analysis of this research.

5.3. Future Recommendation

This research has its limitation on some criteria's which should be considered in the future research. First is the sample size i.e. in this study sample size used is small and restraint to one city only, in future it can work through a large sample size data and in more than one city and then the result can be more accurately apply on the population.

Second is the short time period taken to complete the research i.e. in 6 months in very less finance which limits the study to progress at profitable rate and in future with more time period spend on the research with large finance the results or findings can predictably be more generalize on the population and be supported from other researchers.

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